

Overview of the PHENIX Detector

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PHENIX Detector - First Year Physics Run

***First and foremost:
Klaus Dehmelt's talk at the 2018 PHENIX School***

An excellent and very detailed (100 slides!), technically oriented description of the PHENIX detector

You will find it – along with many other information on PHENIX – at the new collaboration webpage

<https://phenixcollaboration.github.io/web/detectors/overview.html>

or directly on Zenodo

https://zenodo.org/record/3885936#.YMu_h6EpCUk

Please visit, make use of and comment on our new webpage!

<https://phenixcollaboration.github.io/web/>

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Back in 1991: The charge for a new RHIC detector

Letter to the spokespersons of the precursor proposals Sep 9, 1991 → build one single experiment together!

September 9, 1991

Prof. P. Braun-Munzinger
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Prof. S. Nagamiya
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Dr. G. Young
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Dear Peter, Shoji and Glenn:

This is to confirm the discussion we had on Tuesday, September 3, 1991 regarding the decisions made by the Program Advisory Committee with respect to your RHIC Letters of Intent.

1. The Committee decided to reject all three of the Letters of Intent because of what were felt to be major deficiencies in each of them.
2. The Committee decided to place the emphasis on a detector designed to study electrons and photons emerging from the QGP. In this regard, it will address some of the basic physics interests of each of your groups.
3. The Laboratory has appointed Sam Aronson as Spokesman and Project Director with the charge of developing a new collaboration to design and build such a detector. We strongly urge each of you and your current respective collaborators to join in this effort. Those of you who are primarily interested in hadron physics will be welcomed by the STAR collaboration which has been empowered to build a large TPC detector.
4. The Laboratory is prepared to contribute at most \$30 million to the design and construction of this detector. Hopefully, you can find resources outside of the Laboratory to augment this sum.
5. It is hoped that the new collaboration can present a conceptual design to the Technical Advisory Committee in mid December. Sam Aronson will have final authority as to the technical and scientific content of the proposal. He is in the process of forming an advisory committee composed primarily of the leadership of the three former collaborations to assist in the conceptual design.

Although I realize that each of you is very disappointed, I hope that you will find it possible to become a part of this effort. We need all of you in order to maximize our probability of success.

Sincerely,

Mel Schwartz
Associate Director
High Energy and Nuclear Physics

MS:laz
cc: HENP PAC Membership

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(Di)Electrons and (di)photons – think π^0 -- priority
→ pair acceptance!

Insufficient money for full azimuthal coverage.
How do you split the detector into two arms?

Why is the PHENIX acceptance asymmetric?

Delta phi (pair) acceptance

Why this funny shape (arms not back-to-back)?

Optimize pair acceptance!
Increasing $\Delta \phi \rightarrow$ decreasing p_T

With arms back-to-back we would have zero acceptance at 90°

Yes, this decreases dijet acceptance, but dijets were not emphasized in the original charge

Identifying particles – long lifetime ($> 10^{-8}$ sec, $c\tau > 3$ m) measure the particle “directly”

Examples: π , K, γ , ρ , n, ...

Charge (if any!) and 4-momentum needed for PID

4-momentum can be determined from **at least two** of these quantities:

energy

calorimetry

Fully stop the particle
Convert its energy to
- light, charge...
Collect and read out

3-momentum

tracking

Follow path of charged
particles in magnetic
field – get momentum
from curvature

velocity

time-of-flight + pathlength
or Cherenkov-effect

$$\cos(\alpha) = 1/\beta n$$

**Identifying particles – short lifetime ($\ll 10^{-8}$ sec, $c\tau < \text{few cm}$)
measure the particle from its (long-lived) decay products**

Several devices will have to cooperate to identify the two electrons and measure their momentum

But **why three?** Didn't we just say **any two** of quantities p , v , E is sufficient to measure four-momentum?

Improve signal/background!

PHENIX: the original goals (“Shoji plot”)

Signatures of Quark-Gluon Plasma

Shoji Nagamiya was our first spokesperson

His summary plot on various signatures of the QGP as expected in the early 1990s

“Measure as many signals as possible **simultaneously**” (note some deviation from the original charge)

Called for an open-geometry, high-rate capable detector with many different subsystems

Conspicuously **missing** some signals anticipated already back then, like **strangeness enhancement**, **jet suppression** (one of our first claim to fame!) and **flow**. (STAR’s business?)

Yet the design was sufficiently flexible and general to allow for **extremely impactful results** even in those “neglected” areas.

PHENIX at the time of the White Papers (QM2005, Yasuyuki Akiba)

The matter is dense

The matter modifies jets

The matter may melt but regenerate J/psi's

We look forward to working with the theory community to extract the properties of the matter

The matter is strongly coupled

The matter is hot

Overview of the PHENIX Detector – magnets

Muon magnets: different size
Full ϕ
Acceptance $1.1 < \eta < 2.2$
(11-37 degrees)

PHENIX – MAGNETS

Central magnet:
two coils, inner, outer
→ can get ~0 field in the center
→ can maximize field for high p_T

B_r (red) near zero: tracking easier

K. Dehmelt

PHENIX overview – global detectors

Global detectors:

- interaction trigger → BBC
- vertex, T0 → BBC
- centrality (impact parameter) → ZDC+BBC, then BBC only
- reaction plane → BBC, MPC, RXNP

PHENIX, the onion

The fundamental scheme moving out radially:

vertex (including displaced)

momentum (tracking)

particle ID

energy (EMCal)

For the muon arms:

vertex (including displaced)

absorption of hadrons

momentum (tracking)

muon identification

PHENIX subdetectors: BBC

64 elements both N and S side
Cherenkov-radiators
20 ps timing resolution

• **Z-Vertex** = $\frac{T_S - T_N}{2} \times c$

• **Time zero** = $\frac{T_S + T_N - 2L/c}{2}$

$T_{N/S}$: average hit time, c : light velocity, L : 144.35 cm

PHENIX subdetectors: ZDC/SMD/(FCAL)

Spectator neutrons will not be deflected by the DX magnets (and spectator protons will be deflected out of the beampipe)

The “clock-method” to determine centrality

ZDC performance in d+Au

Single neutron in d direction (top)

Single neutron in Au direction (bottom)

SMD performance

Recently: forward neutron A_N and UPC collisions

PHENIX subdetectors: DC

It is outside (after) the magnetic field

Particle is **assumed** to come from the collision vertex

Spatial resolution 120 μm , angular (α) 1 mrad

Very low momentum: particles curl up (invisible)

Momentum resolution decreases with increasing p_T

Hough-transform in $\phi - \alpha$ space

Thanks, DC!

PHENIX subdetectors: PC

Three layers of MWPC-s, behind the DC, RICH and
 in front of the EMCal, typically 300 μm resolution
 PC1 \rightarrow z-coordinate of tracks, θ angle ($R = 2.5$ m)
 PC2 \rightarrow behind the RICH ($R = 4.2$ m), matching
 PC3 \rightarrow matching, charged particle veto in front of EMCal ($R = 5.0$)
 Charged particle multiplicity
 Tricky read-out

FIG. 4. Charged-particle pseudorapidity density per participant pair vs. the number of participants. Predictions from HIJING [2] and EKRT [3] models, and a simple phenomenological fit are also shown. The shaded area represents the systematic errors of $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ and N_p . The errors of N_c are in Table 1.

Figure from the **very first**
 PHENIX publication

PHENIX subdetectors for PID: TOFE

Located in the East arm, in front of the PbGI EMCAL

Plastic scintillator slats, read out by phototubes on both ends (time and position!)

Overall resolution 120 ps

A physics result:

Φ from $\phi \rightarrow KK$ decay
(mass 1.02 GeV, no mass shift!)

PHENIX subdetectors for PID: TOFW

Multigap Resistive Plate Chambers (MRPC)

82 ps resolution (including BBC)

		Pion-Kaon separation	Kaon-Proton separation
TOF	$\sigma \sim 100$ ps	0 - 2.5	- 5
RICH	$n=1.00044$ $\gamma_{th} \sim 34$	5 - 17	17 -
Aerogel	$n=1.01$ $\gamma_{th} \sim 8.5$	1 - 5	5 - 9

Pion time shifted to zero, pion-kaon-proton separation at 1 GeV/c

PHENIX subdetectors for PID: Aerogel (ACC)

Aerogel: solid, transparent, $n = 1.01$
(virtually invisible)

ACC wall, red is the Cherenkov radiator (at fixed R)

Cherenkov-radiator aerogel, light integrating box, read out by two phototubes

Physics performance at 2 GeV/c

PHENIX subdetectors: RICH

$\beta > 1/n \rightarrow$ electrons always move with \sim speed of light
 Pions below 4 GeV/c don't produce Cherenkov light
 Main device for electron ID (major focus of PHENIX!)
 Designed for ethane, operated with CO₂
 Huge improvement in signal / background

Green: Raw spectra Black: Cherenkov hit required
 Blue: Estimated background Red: Background subtracted

PHENIX subdetectors: EMCal

Outermost layer in the central arm.

Energy: **electromagnetic (full containment)**, hadronic (partial)

8 sectors, 6 with lead scintillator (sampling), PbSc,

2 with lead glass (Cherenkov) PbGl. PMT readout.

500-800 ps timing resolution (some hadron rejection; unique for neutrons and antineutrons).

Part of the **high energy particle trigger**

(alone and combined with RICH info, ERT)

“T-shirt plot” → Results from EMCal

FIG. 2. Schematic of the EMCal fast trigger summing operation

PHENIX subdetectors: Muon arms

Muon TRackers:
3 layers in the magnetic field
after absorber (deplete hadrons)

Muon Identifier:
5 gaps between thick steel plates
(only muons survive)

The “muon T-shirt plot”

PHENIX subdetectors: HBD

“Hadron-blind” detector

Direct photons at low p_T (“thermal”)

PHENIX subdetectors: RXNP

Flow measurements require good reaction plane resolution.

RXNP has 2 layers of scintillators, with converter material in front (photons also contribute to RP!)

Installed 2007

Ψ_2 resolution

Ψ_2 and Ψ_3 resolution

PHENIX subdetectors: MPC

A forward electromagnetic calorimeter
 PbWO₄ crystals (240/arm)
 Hamamatsu S8664-55 APD
 Low-noise preamp
 Not shown: driver board,
 5cm apart (air/N₂ cooling)
 LED monitoring

η mesons in the MPC (PRD 90, 072008 (2014))

Fig 3.1: Side View of the proposed MPC locations, one each in the North and South Muon Piston Hole.

PHENIX subdetectors: MPC-EX

PHENIX subdetectors: VTX

- 2 layers of Si pixel detectors ($R=2.6$ and 5.1 cm), $X/X_0 = 1.26\%$
- 2 layers of Si stripixel detectors ($R=11.7$ and 16.6 cm)
- Tracking close to the beampipe – distance of closest approach (DCA)
- Charm and bottom identification / separation
- Charm-enriched: $|DCA| < 200 \mu\text{m}$
- Bottom-enriched: $300 \mu\text{m} < |DCA| < 1000 \mu\text{m}$

(a) Pixel

(b) Stripixel

(c) VTX Front View

(d) VTX Side View

PHENIX subdetectors: FVTX

Charged particle tracking in front of the muon arms, covering $1.2 < |\eta| < 2.2$ in pseudorapidity. Position resolution about 24-28 μm , DCA $< 200 \mu\text{m}$

Fig. 20. A completed half-detector, with the VTX barrels in the center, and the two FVTX endcaps on either end. The overall length is 80 cm.

Each side (endcap, before the muon arm) has 4 layers of Si sensors arranged in a disk.

Summary

PHENIX is a very complex, multi-purpose detector

All this was only the big picture, an appetizer

You will **NOT** be able to successfully analyze your data unless you understand the subdetectors involved

There is plenty of educational material available, with more coming → in part as a response to your requests!

Use, peruse, ask... we are here to help!

Good luck to your analysis!

Thanks for your attention!

Backup